

Dr Samuel Moore,
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Busting the myth that open access means lower quality

– Samuel Moore

Publishing books open access encourages innovation while retaining the rigorous processes and quality of traditional publishing.

Open access is just as high quality, just as scholarly as traditional publishing, but parts of academia still perceive it as less prestigious and less valid. As a result, many authors are advised against publishing open access, particularly those in the early stages of their career who are looking to make a name for themselves.

Advice from the top

Senior academics often recommend publishing through established presses as a better, safer way for fledgling academics to advance their careers and gain tenure.

This was the advice given to Dr Samuel Moore, a scholarly communications specialist at Cambridge University Library, who is early on in his career himself. Moore, who has a PhD in Digital Humanities, has already published two books open access and is soon to publish his first monograph - *Publishing Beyond the Market: Open Access, Care and the Commons* - through the University of Michigan Press.

Moore disputes the suggestion that open access is inferior in quality to traditional presses. He says it is all about perception and established norms, rather than reality. He said:

“ It’s completely untrue that open access books are of lower quality. Publishing open access felt to me like a traditional publishing experience in terms of copy editing, peer reviews and such like.

The emergence of scholar-led presses

Moore is one of the Radical Open Access Collective organisers, a community of scholar-led, not-for-profit presses, journals and other open access projects. He says open access facilitates community-led publishing, which he thinks is a very exciting, positive development.

“A lot of the presses that I like are scholar-led presses that are really embedded within their academic disciplines. Automatically, you have this quality to it, because it’s being not just submitted by an expert, it’s being shaped by an expert in the field, edited by one and sometimes even copy edited by one.”

Experimentation and innovation

Open access facilitates innovation, enabling academics to create and publish research in different formats. By advising early career researchers to stick with traditional publishing presses and methods, Moore thinks academia is missing the opportunity to explore new possibilities and new ways of reaching audiences. Moore explains:

“ We don’t just have to produce books that follow the standard book format. There are many other ways to present research – remixed books, for example. And you can incorporate sound and video.

Giving voice to early career researchers

As the next generation of academics emerges, Moore says they will have their own ideas about how to produce research and will want to experiment. He thinks those ideas should be encouraged and allowed to flourish.

“A while ago, Cambridge University Library hosted a workshop with early career researchers. All of them had these really amazing, in-depth ideas of what they would do if they were allowed to publish in a different way. We had presentations from people talking about using archives in interesting ways or using rapid publishing, for example.”

Attitudes are changing, but Moore thinks it will take time for perceptions of open access to fully change.